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FOLLOW NEOLIVER TO SEE HOW WE ARE DELIVERING A DISRUPTIVE, LIFE-SAVING ALTERNATIVE TO DONOR ORGAN SHORTAGES

AUTOMATED GENERATION OF DENSE, FUNCTIONAL AND PERFUSABLE BIOPRINTED LIVER CONSTRUCTS FOR TRANSPLANTATION

PROJECT FACTS:

Start date: **01/01/2025**

End date: **31/12/2028**

Duration: **48 months**

EU budget: **7.9M€**

Call: **HORIZON-HLTH-2024-TOOL-11**

Topic: **HORIZON-HLTH-2024-TOOL-11-02**

Project number: **101191649**

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PROJECT OVERVIEW

Despite remarkable advancements in organ transplantation, the shortage of transplantable organs remains critical.

EACH year, 25% of patients with end-stage liver disease on the donor waiting list tragically pass away, highlighting the urgent need for alternatives to organ donations.

BIOPRINTING offers a groundbreaking solution, enabling the creation of organs from scratch. However, this technology faces significant technical, biological, and procedural challenges.

NEOLIVER project aims to overcome these hurdles by developing large, dense, and vascularized bioprinted liver constructs that are fully functional and suitable for transplantation.

REVOLUTIONIZING LIVER TRANSPLANTATION WITH BIOPRINTING

NEOLIVER APPROACH

Generate millions of multicellular spheroids from patient-derived organoids.

Bioprint spheroids using laser-induced forward transfer (LIFT) to create vascularized liver constructs.

Integrate functional blood vessels to engineer the first autologous liver ready for transplantation.

Validate safety and efficacy in immune-deficient pigs as a preclinical model.

Develop a clinical validation plan, scaling strategy and a health technology assessment for first-in-human trials.

